

Preservation in the context of EOSC. Sustainable repositories curating digital objects from a long term FAIR enabling perspective

The broad coverage, and wide network connections of the EOSC Association's Long Term Data Preservation Task Force (LTDP-TF) membership have provided valuable insight into the range of assumptions and perspectives around digital preservation. In seeking to investigate, consult and consolidate these viewpoints into recommendations for preservation in the EOSC at European, national and institutional level it became clear that preservation must be set within its wider context.

In this paper we present the frame of reference that has emerged to guide the approach of the Task Force.

The pre-digital history of collecting, maintaining, protecting and sharing information with a long term perspective sits squarely within thousands of years of library practitioners working on books and manuscripts. The emergence of digital data presented new challenges and opportunities for the storage, care and analysis of human knowledge. As the beneficial side of business, academic, political and personal dependence on digital information increased, the risks associated with digital storage, formats and representation also emerged.

A strategic risk benefit approach to identify the financial, operational and reputational risks related to preservation action, and inaction, is needed. Identification of risks should include the availability of appropriate skills to fulfil roles and deliver critical infrastructures services, legal frameworks etc. Risk registers at different levels of governance, including EOSC, must be aligned and should identify preservation-specific risks. Despite the benefits of holding information in digital form, such a risk analysis approach can help quantify the challenges of ensuring digital objects'¹ storage, integrity, provenance and fitness for use over time.

As standards for records and archival management were published from the International Standards Organisation (ISO)^{2,3} in the early 21st Century the conceptual interdependence of 'library' and 'book' was retained. Care of digital objects was always associated with organisational actors taking responsibility on behalf of their creators and users. More recently the roles and responsibilities of these archival and records management bodies have been further defined through 'trustworthy digital repository' (TDR) standards^{4,5,6}.

¹ any collation of data and metadata

² ISO 15489-1:2016 Information and documentation — Records management — Part 1: Concepts and principles <https://www.iso.org/standard/62542.html>

³ ISO 14721:2012 Space data and information transfer systems — Open archival information system (OAIS) — Reference model <https://www.iso.org/standard/57284.html>

⁴ ISO 16363:2012 Space data and information transfer systems — Audit and certification of trustworthy digital repositories <https://www.iso.org/standard/56510.html>

⁵ nestor Seal for Trustworthy Digital Archives

https://www.langzeitarchivierung.de/Webs/nestor/EN/Zertifizierung/nestor_Siegel/siegel.html

⁶ CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051012>

If these repositories exhibit the principles of TRUST⁷ covering transparency, responsibility, user focus, sustainability and technology, then the digital object perspective is represented by FAIR. The FAIR Principles⁸ that data and metadata should be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable have gained traction and focussed attention on long-standing efforts, in particular within research data management spheres. Adoption and development of FAIR is increasingly global⁹, however within Europe much of the FAIR growth has aligned with the development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) to “provide European researchers, innovators, companies and citizens with a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and reuse data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes.”¹⁰. The need for data and metadata to *remain* FAIR is not explicit in the FAIR principles, FAIR-enabling repositories can ensure that digital objects remain FAIR over time through preservation.

A successful EOSC necessitates engagement with a broad range of actors from researchers, to technologists, data management practitioners and policy makers. The focus on trustworthiness and FAIR digital objects is welcome, but implies a need to define and communicate some specialist and complex practices to a wider audience of actors that participate in one or more stages of the digital object management life cycle. Preservation is a case in point where historically a researcher might simply hand their outputs to a trusted repository, or seek data from a repository on the assumption that it would remain understandable and usable after some time had passed. The LTDP TF needs to contextualise the role of preservation both within the wider researcher lifecycle and across the federated and consolidated network of partners that deliver scientific infrastructure (meta)data services. A failure to preserve digital objects as FAIR over time might result in the retention of digital objects (with associated costs) that have a reduced potential for reuse.

In addition to providing a vision for EOSC preservation that includes a future network of trustworthy digital repositories, the task force needs to consider the roles and the financial implications of preservation, including the potential costs of inaction. This remit presents challenges for a topic area that is closely aligned with other data and metadata management areas, while having its own unique and distinct characteristics. Many research data management activities are necessary, but not sufficient, to deliver preservation. Many research data management roles, costs, and risks form part of, but are not unique to, preservation.

⁷ The TRUST Principles for digital repositories <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>

⁸The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

⁹ <https://codata.org/worldfair-global-cooperation-on-fair-data-policy-and-practice-kick-off-meeting-introduces-major-new-initiative-to-advance-implementation-of-the-fair-data-principles>

¹⁰ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

For effective communication the first priority becomes clarification of how preservation works alongside other research data management activities, and how repositories that offer preservation services are similar to and different from other repositories and data services.

The functions and activities of all data services have a foundational dependency on effective storage that ensures integrity and protects from unintended changes, whether accidental or malicious. The lack of a single, referenceable set of minimum storage criteria -in terms of number of copies, locations and media - provides an indicator of how challenging it can be to reach community consensus. The definitions and expectations of data services, including those providing long term preservation, are even more complex to define and agree. Though the standards and associated tests of, and credit for, compliance (including certification) are necessary and desirable, they must be seen as forming a part of the emerging journey towards TRUST and FAIR. At this stage of development no data service or digital object should be excluded from the EOSC due to standards that act as over-strict gatekeepers. The consensus within the task force is that transparency is a priority. This includes transparency on the current status of repositories at organizational infrastructure, digital object management actions, technology and security levels, as well as on the roadmap towards improvement of TRUST and FAIR, This will increase the knowledge base of funders, repositories and other data services, and increase the trust of digital object depositors and reusers.

Trustworthy digital repository standards such as CoreTrustSeal must go beyond the strict scope of 'preservation' activities when certifying organisations. Sustainable preservation depends on sustainable organisations, technology and security in addition to digital object management. An assessment of the CoreTrustSeal applicability to wider data services¹¹ identified that only the specific requirements for Preservation [Requirement R09] and ReUse [R13] were unique to 'TDR' candidate repositories. The paper asserted, and internal review by the LTDP TF agreed, that the other CoreTrustSeal Requirements were applicable across all organisations offering services related to data and metadata. This paper was followed by a crosswalk against CoreTrustSeal of a wide range of current standards, criteria and attributes of repositories and data services¹². Despite a small number of additional functions and activities it displays a strong alignment with the 'core' of the CoreTrustSeal and does not present any additional data service functions that are critical to preservation. This supports the LTDP-TF use of CoreTrustSeal as a key contextual reference point and aligns with the Task Force's proposed perspectives of preservation outcomes, systems and actions.

"Preservation Outcomes: these concern digital objects that, having been curated for FAIRness and other desirable characteristics, are maintained to retain those characteristics for as long as necessary. These outcomes are targeted at a defined and 'designated community' of users.

¹¹ Review of CoreTrustSeal Applicability to non-Preservation (Trustworthy) Data Services
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7646134>

¹² Repository & (Meta)Data Services Activities & Functions Overview
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7689090>

Preservation Systems: accept the deposit of digital objects for storage and access (making them ‘repositories’ in the broad sense) and also curate them with a long term FAIR-enabling perspective on the objects and their designated community (making them candidate to become ‘trustworthy digital repositories’). The designated community’s knowledge base and technological needs are understood and monitored over time. These systems have sufficient resources, including personnel and financial resources, to be sustainable in terms of their organisational, technology and security infrastructure.

Preservation Actions: are the changes to digital objects’ (metadata and data) that are intended to keep them FAIR over time. These actions include technical steps such as emulation or transformations to modern, in-demand, file formats and metadata schemas; but also actions to ensure that the conceptual content of data and metadata, including semantic artefacts such as ontologies, continues to be understood and re-usable.”

EOSC Preservation: Overview Discussion Paper <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7516259>¹³

Any research data information management system offering services around data or metadata is taking actions to achieve defined outcomes. To clarify the preservation context we can reference the curation and preservation levels¹⁴ proposed by the CoreTrustSeal. The response and feedback, including from the task force members, on these proposed levels has been overall favourable, though has suggested that level C (below) could be split to differentiate between deposit standards (D) and initial curation (C)¹⁵. The levels envisage different tiers of service for any digital object that is not simply distributed unchanged from the state in which it was deposited (classified as level zero 0). Quoted, indented text below is taken from the CoreTrustSeal discussion paper.

Level C delivers basic compliance and/or curation’.

“Data content and supporting metadata deposited are checked at the point of deposit for compliance with defined criteria for data formats and metadata elements. If these criteria are not met the digital objects are returned to the depositor for change, or the repository undertakes the necessary curation steps to ensure they comply. Minimal curation for initial access and use, but no long term preservation.”

¹³ Some of this context is provided in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7516259>, which will be repeated to provide background to the consultative and iterative recommendations of the group.

¹⁴ Curation & Preservation Levels: CoreTrustSeal Discussion Paper <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6908019>

¹⁵ UK Data Service (UKDS) Response to the CoreTrustSeal Curation & Preservation Levels Discussion Paper <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7828046>

In EOSC context the envisioned interoperability framework¹⁶ might include certain rules for repositories to ensure that a digital object meets some defined FAIR criteria. A repository system that takes initial curation actions to enable FAIRness, but makes no longer term commitment is not providing active preservation.

Level B delivers 'Logical-Technical Curation'

"In addition to C above the repository takes long-term responsibility for ensuring that the data and metadata are updated over time to newer standards and formats in response to:

- i. technical risks (e.g. file format obsolescence) and/or
- ii. the changing needs of the designated community (e.g. newer alternate formats become necessary for reuse). "

In the context of EOSC preservation there is the opportunity to support preservation repositories in identifying technical risks and the needs of the user communities. This could be achieved through a mixture of developing technical and good practice community networks, developing a risk based approach to monitoring change (e.g. as a part of format registries¹⁷) and providing supporting technologies and services to undertake format migration. In some environments the emulation of software environments provides a more effective route than format migration. Emerging work to align trustworthy repositories and their FAIRenabling activities will become more defined as the technical and community needs define what FAIR means for different disciplines and domains.

Level A delivers 'Conceptual preservation for understanding and reuse'

"In addition to B and C above the repository monitors changes to the definition and demands of their designated community, including their knowledge base, and takes responsibility for the preservation actions that ensure digital objects can be understood and re-used. Usually this will involve updates to the content of metadata elements and other semantic artifacts such as controlled vocabularies and ontologies. For some repositories it may include responsibility for editing the structure and content of deposited data."

The work of the task force, and the EOSC as a whole, must take account of the fact that within and beyond these levels, different institutions, nations, domains and disciplines have different expectations from their trustworthy repository data services. In some cases e.g. within the social sciences, a repository is the last stage of (research, government, administrative) data validation before access. In cooperation with data depositors and owners repositories may be asked to update values, weighting, identify outlying variables etc. that need correction or refinement. This level of engagement with the data may be uncommon, but to ensure ongoing understandability and reusability by users there may be a need to update the metadata and ontologies that surround the target data. This can include the generation of new versions of digital objects

¹⁶ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K., et al., EOSC interoperability framework : report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

¹⁷ E.g. <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/>

through the application of new geographical regions or country ontologies, updating or moving to new subject ontologies, revising descriptive metadata to support new resource discovery systems etc. These actions at Level A all deliver outcomes that would not be delivered by the more technical actions provided at Level B.

It is clear from the tiers provided above that to deliver active preservation at level B or A a repository will also need to set criteria for deposit and/or undertake initial curation (C) for standards compliance. In addition, the repository will need to provide *at least* the same level of digital object management, organisational infrastructure, technology and security that would apply to any data services. So, while preservation is not simply the provision of deposit, storage, curation and access, all of these remain necessary for repositories delivering preservation. It is important for the LTDP TF to present recommendations that both acknowledge this fact and address the unique functions, activities and roles that long term preservation implies. These unique factors represent the *additional* function, activities, roles and costs implied by a decision to preserve. Though some work has been done to look at individual research data management costs¹⁸ and to calculate the costs of curation¹⁹, these don't provide granular, standardised costs or differentiate costs between initial curation and long term preservation. Active preservation may reasonably be assumed to represent an additional cost over lower levels of care, but the degree of additional cost is not known in comparison to basic retention and curation costs. The converse cost calculation would be to analyse cases where digital objects that have been retained lose their reuse value because they have not been actively preserved.

As any decision to retain digital objects at any level of storage, curation or preservation undeniably has some costs there is a need to consider appraisal. Decisions about whether to retain digital objects, and the longer term care they should benefit from, may initially be driven by funders, researchers creating or collecting data, or at the point of deposit in a repository.

Defining the value of digital objects is perhaps even more challenging than defining the cost of their care. A decision taken at project conception by funders and instantiated in a data management plan (DMP²⁰) may not be supported by the research process or outcomes. As multi-disciplinary research becomes more practical and common there may be a wider set of potential re-users with their own perspective on the value of digital objects. As time passes interest in a digital object may reduce, or it may become just as easy to reproduce an object as to retain and preserve it. If the value of a digital object is derived from direct reuse in research, this may imply a simpler object (and therefore lower costs) than if the value is derived from the ability to reproduce and revalidate older research.

If preservation is the ability to identify and deliver managed changes that ensure value is maintained, then we must also consider re-appraisal over time to ensure that the return on investment is maintained. Researchers, as depositors and reusers, need to know how long a digital object will be retained in its current state, whether it is being preserved for ongoing

¹⁸ <https://www.curationexchange.org/>

¹⁹ <https://www.4cproject.eu/>

²⁰ E.g. <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/>

usability, and how and when a decision might be taken to change the level of care. In an ideally interoperable EOSC, a transparent decision to reduce the level of care (or even to delete) a pathology digital object by a Life Sciences repository would be visible to a Social Science repository. The latter may wish to take over responsibility for the object.

As the LTDP TF consolidates and communicates the context and implications above into draft recommendations it will seek validation, feedback and guidance on the direction of travel and speed of change that are practical for initial standards development and for widespread adoption.

Where possible the task force will propose statements and make recommendations that are generally applicable. They will focus on the development of broad policies and guidance where relevant bodies have influence, and focus on direct practice and infrastructure where those bodies have control.

European

European level actors including, but not limited to the EC, the EOSC Association and global standards bodies, networks and membership organisations with a European reach. Including pan-European and global funding organisations.

National

Governmental entities, standards bodies, networks and membership organisations. National service providers contributing to the EOSC.

Institutional

Research performing organisations, higher education institutions, and others at national and regional levels.

Conclusion

The task force vision is that the digital objects made findable and accessible through repository environments, are subject to appraisal and reappraisal over time to assess their value, impact, and associated costs. This informs the levels of storage, curation and preservation required. Not all digital objects need to be preserved, but if long term need and usage potential have been identified, then preservation can maintain and bring new value to data and metadata for their communities of users. The task force has therefore been explicit in defining what preservation means in the context of EOSC, stating that systems claiming to deliver preservation outcomes, need to be sustainable and to curate digital objects from a long-term FAIR enabling perspective.

Appraisal, reappraisal, other aspects of digital object management, organisational infrastructure, technology, and security will all benefit from a risk benefit analysis approach.

Criteria for FAIR objects, aligned with those for trustworthy digital repositories, such as CoreTrustSeal provide an important reference point for evaluating digital objects and the services that support them. Rather than setting strict certification criteria for engagement with EOSC, trust and FAIRenabling practices are the end goal in an ongoing journey for many repositories. By providing the necessary level of transparency around current levels of FAIRness and trustworthiness of repositories for data depositors, funders, and users, the numerous partners across the EOSC can better understand and inform each other.